

EVALUATION OF CREEP-LESS COMPOSITES USING TG-LESS EPOXY RESIN AS THE MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to create a creep-less composite material reinforced with carbon fiber, which is expected to be applicable to parts that are continuously loaded in automotive application. The method to achieve this subject is using T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrix of composite material. That's because in the viscoelastic behaviour of cured T_g -less epoxy resin, the storage modulus does not drop and maintains a high level as if it were in glassy state even at an elevated temperature such as 300°C, and additionally the loss tangent is always low in all testing temperature range. This fact might mean stress relaxation hardly occurs and this resin enables to create a creep-less composite material.

By the way, T_g -less epoxy resin was easily obtained by curing with a salt of alkaline metal and carboxylic acid. Investigation of the curing process of epoxy resin mixture with potassium carboxylates revealed that the curing reaction was initiated from the nucleophilic addition of $-\text{COO}^-$ to the epoxy group to form an ester linkage and then the chain propagation subsequently occurred by anionic ring opening polymerization of the epoxy group to form ether linkages. On the basis of the results, it was suggested that the mechanism of ' T_g -disappearing phenomenon' was closely linked to uniformly dense cross-linking density.

On the other hand, T_g -less epoxy resin has a weak point of being brittle because of suppressed relaxation. Modifying with nano-rubber particle effectively improved the resin's toughness. Finally, creep tests were conducted by 3-point bending mode for carbon fiber reinforced composite materials using the modified or unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrices. As a result, in the case of T_g -less epoxy resin containing 16 wt% of nano-rubber particle, the creep strain rate became almost zero after testing time was over 50 h.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resin has high mechanical and electrical performance with good handling properties. As such, it is one of the most typical and widely used thermosets [1]. In ordinary cases, cured resins have a glass transition temperature (T_g). Storage modulus of ordinary epoxy resin after curing maintains high values, in the order of 10^9 Pa until the temperature reaches its T_g and then drops to low values, in the order of 10^7 Pa above the T_g . The state of resin below T_g is called to be in glassy state and the state above T_g in rubbery state. At that time, loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) shows a small value less than 0.05 sufficiently below or above the T_g , and shows a large value more than 0.5 around the T_g , i.e. the temperature range of glassy state-rubbery state transition, when the testing frequency is 1Hz.

On the other hand, we have found that T_g -less cured resin was easily obtained by curing a standard epoxy resin with a salt of alkaline metal and carboxylic acid as a curing catalyst [2]-[5]. In this system, the storage modulus of the cured resin did not drop and maintained a high level as if it were in glassy state even at an elevated temperature such as 300°C. In response to this phenomenon, the loss tangent is always low in all temperature range up to 300°C. This fact might mean stress relaxation hardly occurs, hence there is the possibility to create a creep-less composite material by using this resin as the matrix, which is expected to be applicable to parts that are continuously loaded in automotive application.

In this study, therefore, creep tests by 3-point bending mode were performed about CFRP using T_g -

less epoxy resin as the matrix at 100, 150 or 200°C.

By the way, the T_g -less epoxy resin has a weak point to be weaker and more brittle than ordinary epoxy resins because stress-relaxation is suppressed, where crack tends to easily propagate straight. This brittleness of resin itself reduces the initial strength of composite using it as the matrix even at room temperature, resulting in the limitation of application. For the purpose of improving the brittleness, the modification of epoxy resin by dispersing nanometer-sized rubber particle was also investigated.

Fig. 1: Dynamic viscoelastic behavior of cured epoxy resin and T_g -less composite reinforced with glass fiber fabrics. (a) Conventional epoxy resin cured by imidazole; (b) T_g -less epoxy resin cured by potassium carboxylate; (c) Composite using T_g -less epoxy resin

2 TG-LESS EPOXY RESIN

According to previous studies from our laboratory[2]-[5], T_g -less cured resin is easily obtained by curing a conventional epoxy resin such as diglycidylether of bisphenol A catalyzed by a salt of alkaline metal and carboxylic acid. In this system, the storage modulus (E') of cured resin does not drop and maintain a high level, in the order of 10^9 Pa, as if the cured resin were in glassy state even at an elevated temperature such as 300°C as shown in **Fig. 1**-(b) while the E' of an ordinary epoxy resin cured by 1-Methylimidazole drops suddenly to low value, in the order of 10^7 Pa above its T_g (ca.120°C) as shown in **Fig. 1**-(a).

T_g -less epoxy resins are cured by the polymerization mechanism shown in **Fig. 2**. In the first step, addition initiated by nucleophilic attack of a carboxide anion of potassium carboxylate to a β -carbon atom of epoxy group takes place to form an ester linkage. Next, since a newly formed oxide anion has enough nucleophilicity to open another oxirane ring further, anionic polymerization is brought about to form ether linkages progressively.

This polymerization is similar to living polymerization, for example, anionic polymerization of styrene initiated by sodium complex of naphthalene, in terms of the fact that chain transfer is extremely hard to occur. Moreover, because the polymerization catalyzed by potassium carboxylate is fortunately not so sensitive to H_2O or air under ordinary curing condition for epoxy resin, this polymerization system can be widely applied to the field of thermosets.

The formation of T_g -less cured resin is just attributed to this characteristic manner of polymerizing. **Fig. 3** illustrates the network formation process during curing, comparing in T_g -less epoxy resin and in conventional epoxy resin catalyzed by 1-Methylimidazole. Catalyst molecules are dispersed in epoxy

Fig. 2 Polymerization mechanism of T_g -less epoxy resin catalyzed by potassium carboxylate.

Fig. 3: Illustration for the network formation process during the curing of epoxy anionically catalyzed by carboxylates with alkaline metals or conventional catalysts.

monomers in the initial state as shown in (a). The polymerization of epoxy monomers is initiated from the catalyst molecules as shown in (b). Although the polymerization proceeds linearly because of anionic ring-opening polymerization, cross-linked network is automatically formed with propagating whenever the epoxy monomers are di-functional or more. In the case of 1-Methylimidazole, chain transfer and/or termination occur frequently during the curing. So, the network to be formed should have many defects, which lead to form partially sparse network in dense network even after complete consumption of epoxy groups as shown in (d). On the other hand, in the potassium carboxylate case, chain transfer and/or termination hardly occur. So, the network to be formed should have extremely few defects and its cross-linking density is uniformly high as shown in (c). The motion of main chain

of cured resin corresponding to the micro Brownian movement must be suppressed in the very highly cross-linked network like (c) even at higher temperature. This is precisely the mechanism of T_g -disappearance.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials

JER828 (Bisphenol A type epoxy resin; epoxy equivalent weight 190 g/eq) was available from Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation. XNH6853 (potassium carboxylate) and 1-Methylimidazole were purchased from Nagase ChemteX Corporation and Tokyo Chemicals Co. Ltd., respectively. All reagents were used without further purification.

Rubber particle modification of epoxy resin was conducted by dispersing nanometer-sized or micrometer-sized acrylic rubber particle into bisphenol A-type liquid epoxy resin in the content of 16 or 32 wt%. Corresponding samples (TGL-0A, TGL-5A, TGL-6A and TGL-7A) were provided by Nagase ChemteX Corporation.

3.2 Methods

Dynamic viscoelastic measurements with bending mode for various cured resins were performed using a viscoelastic spectrometer, DMS-6100 made by SEIKO Instruments Co., Ltd. at a frequency of 1Hz (bending mode) and a heating rate of 2°C/min.

3.3 Preparation of epoxy resin mixtures

All epoxy resin mixtures were prepared with special attention to the complete dispersion of the paste including potassium carboxylate in the liquid resin. Each of the prepared mixtures was held at 60°C for 15 min *in vacuo* for degassing, prior to curing. In this study a step curing process was adopted. In the first step, the resin mixture was heated at 120°C for 2 h. In the second step, the temperature was elevated to 180°C and maintained for 6 h for the completion of curing.

3.4 Preparation of composites using T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrix

GFRP or CFRP was prepared by impregnating T_g -less-type uncured liquid epoxy resin mixture pre-heated at 70°C for reducing its viscosity into glass or carbon fiber fabrics and subsequent pressing and heating them for 2 h at 120°C and for 2 h at 180°C. The fiber content of the GFRP or CFRP was 34 or 45 vol%, respectively.

Fig. 4 Bending strength and modulus of CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin at elevated temperatures. (CO6347 purchased from Toray was used as carbon fiber fabrics. $V_f = 45\%$)

Fig. 5: Creep test at 100, 150 or 200°C for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin.

3.5 Creep test

3-point bending creep test was performed for CFRP specimens at 100, 150 and 200°C for up to 100 h. The loaded stress taken for specimen was 10 % bending strength of each specimen at room temperature unless otherwise stated.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Mechanical properties of composites using T_g -less epoxy resin

The measurement of dynamic viscoelastic behavior for the obtained GFRP, shown in Fig. 1-(c), revealed that the GFRP exhibited a high modulus even around 300°C, especially more than 80% of modulus at 25°C was maintained at 250°C. This tendency was also observed in the static bending test of CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin at elevated temperatures (Fig. 4). Contrary to this, bending strength went down steadily after temperature exceeded 100°C. Moreover, even at the room temperature, bending strength is not so high for 45% in volumetric content of carbon fiber due to brittleness of the matrix resin. In the case that an ordinary epoxy resin were used as the matrix, at least 800 MPa could be expectedly obtained.

On the other hand, creep test at 100, 150 or 200°C for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrix was performed. Creep compliance, D_c , didn't increase up to 100 h of testing time at 100 or 150°C as shown in Fig. 5. This creep-less phenomenon was considered to be attributed to no permission of relaxation in the matrix resin, corresponding to the constantly low value of $\tan \delta$ in the whole temperature range. At 200°C, however, creep compliance started to increase after 10 h. According to another investigation, it was confirmed that this increase in creep compliance was not due to creep itself but due to thermal decomposition of the matrix resin.

4.2 Improvement of brittleness of T_g -less epoxy resin by modification with nanometer-sized rubber particle

As mentioned above, mechanical strength of T_g -less epoxy resin is not high

Fig. 6: Bending stress vs. strain in bending test at 23, 50 and 100°C for neat cured resins:

(a) Unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin, (b) T_g -less epoxy resin modified with rubber nano-particle at the content of 16 wt%.

Fig. 7: Time dependence of creep strain rate at 100°C for various cured epoxy resins.

ref... 1-Methylimidazole cured epoxy resin

TGL-0A... Unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin

TGL-5A... Nano-rubber modified T_g -less epoxy resin (Rubber content: 32%)

TGL-6A... Nano-rubber modified T_g -less epoxy resin (Rubber content: 16%)

TGL-7A... Micro-rubber modified T_g -less epoxy resin (Rubber content: 32%)

due to its brittleness. So, the improvement of brittleness by dispersing nanometer-sized rubber particle in T_g -less epoxy resin was investigated. The result is shown in **Fig. 6**. Bending strength was improved by dispersion of nano-rubber in all testing temperatures from 23 to 100°C. Especially at 23 and 100°C, it was remarkably improved.

Fig. 7 shows the results of creep test at 100°C for various cured resins without reinforcing fiber. The ordinary epoxy resin cured with 1-Methylimidazole always has some value more than zero, which means creep progresses constantly. On the other hand, in the case of T_g -less epoxy resin modified with nano-rubber particle at 16 wt%, the creep strain rate became almost zero after testing time was over 50 h, that means no more creep progresses further. Consequently, a creep-less matrix resin with good mechanical property was successfully developed.

4.3 Evaluation of creep property of CFRP

To evaluate the creep property for carbon fiber reinforced composite using finally formulated T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrix, 3-point bending creep test was conducted at 140°C for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin modified with rubber nano-particle at 16 wt% as well as those using unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin and a conventional epoxy resin cured with 1-Methylimidazole as the matrices for reference. In the test, loaded stresses were 30, 40 and 50% of the rupture stress of each samples. **Fig. 8** shows the change in creep strain with time obtained in this measurement for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin modified with rubber nano-particle at 16 wt% as a representative example. The slope of each point of creep strain curve namely means creep strain rate. So, the slopes of curve were immediately plotted in the graph shown in **Fig. 9** which indicates the relationship between creep strain rate at 140°C and testing time. Because the creep strain rates were all able to be regarded as almost constant after 50 h in testing time passed, the average values of creep strain rate at 140°C in the range between 50 to 90 h in testing time were calculated. The obtained values were plotted in **Fig. 10** whose abscissa indicates the actual stress applied to each specimen, which doesn't depend on the rupture stress of each CFRP. As is clear from this figure, the average creep strain rate of CFRP using modified or unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin as the matrix was always low (almost zero) while that of CFRP using a conventional epoxy resin was much higher and drastically increased when load stress exceeded 180 MPa. On the other hand, in the case of CFRP

Fig. 8: Change in creep strain with time at 140°C under various load stresses for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin modified with rubber nano-particle (16 wt %).

Fig. 9: Change in creep strain rate with time at 140°C under various load stresses for CFRP using T_g -less epoxy resin modified with rubber nano-particle (16 wt %).

using modified or unmodified T_g -less epoxy resin, there was very low dependency on load stress. In addition, there was almost no difference in tendency between the two in spite of CFRP using the modified T_g -less epoxy resin containing as much as 16 wt% of rubbery component in the matrix. This might be because the rubber nano-particles individually existed in the matrix resin separately like isolated islands floating in the sea and don't involve in the relaxation of the matrix resin. If so, it is considered that the rubber nano-particles probably acted as obstacles which impede crack propagation, resulting in effective improvement of bending strength, as shown in **Fig. 6**. The results obtained in this study strongly suggested the possibility of producing creep-less composite materials with good mechanical properties.

Fig. 10: Load stress dependence of average creep strain rate at 140°C in the range from 50-90 h in testing time for the various CFRP specimens.

5 CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The mechanism of curing of epoxy resin by potassium carboxylates is the anionic polymerization initiated by $-\text{COO}-$.
- (2) The curing by potassium carboxylates brings about fully dense cross-linking networks.
- (3) That results in T_g -disappearing phenomenon. Mechanical strength of T_g -less epoxy resin can be successfully improved by rubber nano-particle dispersion.
- (4) The carbon fiber reinforced composite using T_g -less epoxy resin exhibited creep-less property at moderate temperatures.

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